

PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT AS DETERMINANTS OF PUPILS' ACADEMIC ACHEIVEMENT: A CORRELATIONAL STUDY

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8020228>

Published Date: 09-June-2023

Abstract: The study determined the parental involvement as determinants of pupils' academic achievement of Dampil Elementary School: A Correlational study school year 2022 – 2023. Specifically, the study tried to: (1) established pupil – respondents' characteristics in terms of Types of Family, Parents' Participation in School Program; (2) establish the academic achievement of the pupil – respondents' as indicated their Grade Point Average; (3) find out if there is a significant relationship between the academic achievement when grouped to according to the Types of Family and Parents' Participation in School Program.

Statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean and Spearman - rho were used in the analysis of data.

Keywords: Teachers' Burnout and Work Performance.

1. SUMMARY

The subject of the study were the Seventy (70) grade I pupils' of Dampil Elementary School, Division of Misamis Oriental officially enrolled during the school year 2020-2021 and their parents' who attended the school activities.

The study determined the parental involvement as determinants of pupils' academic achievement of Dampil Elementary School: A Correlational study school year 2020 – 2021. Specifically, the study tried to: (1) established pupil-respondents' characteristics in term of Types of Family, Parents' Participation in School Program; (2) establish the academic achievement of the pupil- respondents'' as indicated their Grade Point Average; (3) find out if there is a significant relationship between the academic achievement when grouped to according to the Type of Family and parents' participation in School Program.

Statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean and Spearman rho were used to analysis of data.

2. FINDINGS

Based on the study, the following findings below were summarized:

Table 1.1 presents the data of Frequency and percentage Distribution of the respondents in terms of Type of family. Revealed that majority with a frequency of Forty-Eight (48) or 68.6% of the respondents came from nuclear families.

Table 1.2.1 revealed that question no.1 in academic program majority, thirty-two (32) or 45.7% of the respondents have parents who are *Fairly Participated* in participation in school programs as to academic program. Eighteen (18) or 25.7%

answered their parents *Seldom Participated*; Fourteen (14) or 20% said *Sometimes* their parents participated; and only Six (6) or 8.6% replied that their parents *Always Participated*. Above all, no parents who never participated.

Question no. 2, a highest number of Thirty-One (31) or 44.3% among pupils who responded that their parents, *Seldom Participate* I School Academic Programs. Twelve (12) or 17.1% answered *Always Participated*; seventeen (17) or 24.3% said *Sometimes Participated*; and only Ten (10) or 14.3% fall at *Fairly Participated*. Hence, no one said *Never* their parents participated in school Academic programs.

Twenty-eight (28) or 40% of the respondents have parents who are *Seldom Participated* in participation in school programs us to physical program under question no.1. Only Nine (9) or 12.9% uttered that their parents *Always Participated* in physical programs; Twenty-One (21) or 30% said their parents

Sometimes Participated; Twelve (12) or 17.1% whom their parents Fairly Participated. No one among respondents answered *Never participated*.

In Question no 2. Twenty-eight (28) or 40% the respondents said that their parents *Sometimes Participated*. Sixteen (16) or 22.9% respondent *Always Participated*; Four (4) or 5.7% *Fairly participated* and zero (0) or no one answered *Never* their parents participated in Physical Program.

Question no. 3 About Twenty seven (27) or 38.6% the respondents whose parents where *Sometimes Participated*; Sixteen (16) or 22.9% spoke out that their Parents *Always Participated*; Nineteen (19) or 27% responded *Seldom participated* and Eight (8) or 11.4% said only *Fairly* their Parents Participated in Physical Program.

While question no 4. revealed that majority with Twenty-eight (28) or 40% whos the respondents' parents where *Sometimes participated*. Twenty-Three (23) or 32.9% answered their parents *Seldom participated*; Thirteen (13) or 18.6% said *Always* their parents participated. Above all, no one parents who *Never participated*.

In question no. 5, a highest number of Twenty-Five (25) or 35.7% among parents responded that their parents *Seldom participated* in school physical program. Twenty-four (24) or 34.3% answered *Sometimes participated*; Twelve (12) or 17.1% said *Always participated*; and only Nine (9) or 12.9% fall at Fairly Participated. Hence, no one said *Never* their parents participated in school physical program.

Table 1.2.3 reflected the parents' participation in school program as to clean and green program of the respondents. Revealed in question no. 1 that out of Seventy (70) pupils'-respondent. Twenty-six (26) or 37.1% of them were *Seldom participated*; Seventeen (17) or 24.3% said their parents *Sometimes* and *Always participated*; ten (10) or 14.3% said their parents *Fairly participated*. No one among respondents answered *Never participated* in school Clean and Green program. Question no. 2 Thirty-Three (33) or 47.1% the respondents have parents who are *Sometimes participated*. Sixteen (16) or 22.9% respondent *Always Participated*; Fifteen (15) or 21.4% *Seldom participated*; Six (6) or 8.6 % *Fairly participated* and zero (0) or no one answered *Never* their parents participated in Clean and green program. Question no. 3 About Twenty-eight (28) or 40% the respondents have parents who are *sometimes participated*; Twenty (20) or 28.6% spoke out that their parents *seldom participated*; Seventeen (17) or 24.3% responded *Always participated* and Five (5) or 7.1% said only *Fairly* their Parents Participated in Clean and Green program. And question no 4 revealed that majority, Twenty-five (25) or 35.7% the respondents have parents who are *Sometimes Participated*. Twenty three (23) or 32.9% answered their parents *Seldom participated*; Fourteen (14) or 20% said *Always* their parents participated; and only Eight (8) or 11.4% relied that their parents *Fairly participated*. Above all, no one parents who never participated.

2.1) The 2.1 shows the Frequency and percentage of the Respondents in terms of academic achievement. Thirty-three (33) or 47.1% of the pupils' respondents obtained a grade of *Satisfactory* on their Academic achievement with a grade point average ranging from 80-84. While Nineteen (19) or 27.1% were rated *Very Satisfactory* which grades range from 85 – 90, Only Seven (7) or 10% got an *Outstanding* grade with 90 – above grade point average and Eleven (11) or 15.7% acquired a *Fairly Satisfactory* grade.

3.1) Table 3.1 presents the Correlation between the Academic Achievement of respondents and their family Type. Showed that the computed Spearman rho value of .020 at 0.05 level of probability, has no correlation nor significant relationship.

Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted. Therefore, the parent-respondents' family type the nuclear and extended family did not significantly influences the academic achievement of their children.

3.2) Table 3.2 shows the Data on Correlation between the Academic Achievement and the parents' participation in the School Program. As gleaned by table 3.2 that the computed Spearman rho is .776 for academic program, .535 for physical program and .636 for clean and green program which are greater than 0.05 probability level.

3. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the finding of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The respondents live solely with their father, mother, siblings with or without house help and no additional relatives. This type set-up could be explained by the typical Filipino families with complete members living in one household and sharing together the tasks and household chores. When the children are securely attached to the parents, they are able to explore and master their environment. Children raise nuclear family structure are often stable emotionally and they suffer less emotional problems thereby making them less anxious in the pursuit of their academic work (Kamla – Raj, 2008).
2. Analysis revealed that this result was also supported with the claim that academic achievement score distribution of children whose parents were highly involved in their education was sustainability higher than that of their counterpart whose parents were not involved. Napoles et al. (2009). Revealed that children with directly supportive parents scored highest in the children's test. The study also showed that when parents have a high regard, becomes a motivating force, encouraging the children to do well in school.
3. Thirty-three (33) or 47.1% of the pupils respondents obtained a grade of *Satisfactory* on their academic achievement with a grade point average ranging from 80 – 84. While Nineteen (19) or 27.1% were rated *Very Satisfactory* which grades range from 85 – 90, Only Seven (7) or 10% got an *Outstanding* grade with 90 – above grade point average and eleven (11) or 15.7% acquired a *Fairly satisfactory* grade.

4. RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the findings and conclusions; the following recommendations were presented to the following:

1. Guidance counselor should utilize the study to use as basis for a parenting program and activities that it can influence to their children. Present findings of the study and make it a springboard in the planning of the parenting program and different activities of the school and actualize parenting program.
2. As for the adviser/moderator/school administrator, they should plan a more comprehensive parenting program activity.
3. Parents' should attend parenting seminars sponsored by the school or other concerned institutions to be reminded and be more knowledgeable and skilled in parenting. Promote dialogue and discussion in dealing with the children.
4. Future researchers can make further study with a wider scope can be done to see a broader picture of the implications of parental involvement as determinants of pupils' academic achievement. Additional variables may be included or a broader coverage of the study.

Problem 1. What is the pupil – respondents' profile when grouped according to:

1.1 Type of Family

1.1.1 Nuclear Family

1.1.2 Extended Family

1.2 Participation in School Program

1.2.1 Academic Program

1.2.2 Physical Program

1.2.3 Clean and Green Program

Table 1.1: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the respondents in terms of Type of Family

TYPE OF FAMILY	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Nuclear Family	48	68.6%
Extended Family	22	31.4%
TOTAL	70	100%

The table presents the type of family. Revealed that majority (68.6%) of the respondents came from nuclear families. The respondents live solely with their father, mother, siblings with or without house help and no additional relatives. This type set – up could be explained by the typical Filipino families with complete members living in one household and sharing together the tasks and household chores. When the children are securely attached to the parents, they are able to explore and master their environment. Children raised in nuclear family structure are often stable emotionally and they suffer less emotional problems thereby making them less anxious in the pursuit of their academic work (Kamla – Raj, 2008).

Table 1.2.1: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents in terms of Parents' Participation in School Program as to Academic Program

ACADEMIC PROGRAM	Question no. 1		Question no. 2	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Always Participated	6	8.6%	12	17.1%
Sometimes Participated	14	20%	17	24.3%
Seldom Participated	18	25.7%	31	44.3%
Fairly Participated	32	45.7%	10	14.3%
Never Participated	0	0	0	0
TOTAL	70	100%	70	100%

Table 1.2.1 revealed that question no.1 in academic program majority, Thirty two (32) or 45.7% the respondents have parents who are fairly participated in participation in school programs as to academic program. Question no. 2 revealed that majority, Thirty one (31) or 44.3% the respondents have parents who are seldom participated in participation in school programs as to academic program.

Table 1.2.2: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Parents Participation in School Programs as to Physical Program

PHYSICAL PROGRAM	Question no.1		Question no.2		Question no.3		Question no.4		Question no.5	
	F	P	F	P	F	P	F	P	F	P
Always Participated	9	12.9%	16	22.9%	16	22.9%	13	18.6%	12	17.1
Sometimes Participated	21	30%	28	40%	27	38.6%	28	40%	24	34.3%
Seldom Participated	28	40%	22	31.4%	19	27.1%	23	32.9%	25	35.7%
Fairly Participated	12	17.1%	4	5.7%	8	11.4%	6	8.6%	9	12.9%
Never Participated	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
TOTAL	70	100%	70	100%	70	100%	70	100%	70	100%

Table above revealed that Twenty eight (28) or 40% the respondents have parents who are “*seldom participated*” in participation in school programs as to physical program under question no. 1. Question no.2 revealed that majority, twenty eight (28) or 40% the respondents have parents who are “*sometimes participated*” in participation in school programs as to physical program. About twenty seven (27) or 38.6% the respondents have parents who are “*sometimes participated*” in participation in school programs as to physical program in question no. 3. Question no. 4 revealed that majority, Twenty eight (28) Or 40% the respondents have parents who are “*sometimes participated*” in participation in school programs as to physical program. And for the question no. 5 revealed that majority, Twenty five (25) or 35.7% the respondents have parents who are “*seldom participated*” in participation in school programs in physical program.

Table 1.2.3: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents in terms of Parents' Participation in School Programs as to Clean and Green Program

CLEAN AND GREEN PROGRAM	Question no. 1		Question no. 2		Question no. 3		Question no. 4	
	F	P	F	P	F	P	F	P
Always Participated	17	24.3%	16	22.9%	17	24.3%	14	20%
Sometimes Participated	17	24.3%	33	47.1%	28	40%	25	35.7%
Seldom Participated	26	37.1%	15	21.4%	20	28.6%	23	32.9%
Fairly Participate	10	14.3%	6	8.6%	5	7.1%	8	11.4%
Never Participated	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
TOTAL	70	100%	70	100%	70	100%	70	100%

Table 1.2.3 reflected the parents' participation in school programs as to clean and green program of the respondents. This table revealed in question no.1 that out of Seventy (70) pupils' - respondents. Twenty six (26) or 37.1% of them were "seldom participated" in participation in school programs as to clean and green program. Question no. 2 revealed majority Thirty three (33) or 47.1% the respondents have parents' who are "sometimes participated" in participation in school program as to clean and green program. About Twenty eight (28) or 40% the respondents have parents' who are "sometimes participated" in participation in school programs as to clean and green program. In question no. 3. Lastly, Twenty five (25) or 35.7% the respondents have parents who are "sometimes participated" in participation in school programs as to clean and green program.

2. What is the Academic Achievement of the respondents as categorized below:

- 2.1 Outstanding
- 2.2 Very Satisfactory
- 2.3 Satisfactory
- 2.4 Fairly Satisfactory
- 2.5 Did not meet Expectation

Table 2.1: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Academic Achievement

ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
90 – above - Outstanding (O)	7	10%
85 – 90 - Very Satisfactory (VS)	19	27.1%
80 – 84 - Satisfactory (S)	33	47.1%
75 – 79 - Fairly Satisfactory (FS)	11	15.7%
70 – below - Did not meet Expectation	0	0
TOTAL	70	100%

Table 2.1 shows the Frequency and Percentage of the Respondents in terms of Academic Achievement.

Table above revealed that Thirty-Three (33) or 47.1% of the pupils' respondents obtained a grade of *Satisfactory* on their Academic Achievement with a grade point average ranging from 80-84. While Nineteen (19) or 27.1% were rated *Very Satisfactory* which grades range from 85 – 90, Only Seven (7) or 10% got an *Outstanding* grade with 90- above grade point average and eleven (11) or 15.7% acquired a *Fairly Satisfactory* grade.

3. Is there significant relationship between the Academic Achievement of the respondents and the pupils' profile when grouped according to:

- 3.1 Types of Family
- 3.2 Parents' Participation in School Program

Table 3.1: Data Showing the Distribution on Relationship between the Academic Achievement and the Family Type

TYPE OF FAMILY	Correlation on Academic Achievement (r)	Decision on Ho1
Nuclear Type	.020	Accepted
Extended Type		

Table 3.1 presents the Correlation between the Academic Achievement of respondents and their family type.

Table 3.1 showed that the computed Spearman rho value of .020 at 0.05 level of probability, has no correlation nor significant relationship. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted. Therefore, the parent – respondents' family type the nuclear and extended family did not significantly influence the academic achievement of their children.

Table 3.2: Data Showing the Distribution and Relationship between the Academic Achievement and the Parents' Participation in the School Program

SCHOOL PROGRAM	Correlation on Academic Achievement (r)	Decision on Ho1
Academic Program	.776	rejected
Physical Program	.535	rejected
Clean and Green Program	.636	rejected

Table 3.2 shows the Data on Correlation between the Academic Achievement and the Parents' Participation in the School Program.

As gleaned by table 3.2 that the computed Spearman rho is .776 for academic program, .535 for physical program and .636 for clean and green program which are greater than 0.05 level of significance. This means that parents' participation in school program influenced the pupils' academic achievement. Hence, there is a significant relationship between the Academic Achievement of Respondents to the Parents' participation in the School Program.

Analysis revealed that this result was also supported with the claim that academic achievement score distribution of children whose parents were highly involved in their education was substantially higher than that of their counterpart whose parents were not involved.

Napoles et al. (2009). Revealed that the children with directly supportive parents scored highest in the children's test. The study also showed that when parents have a high regard, become a motivating force, encouraging the children to do well in school.

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